

Apparent molar volumes of malonic and succinic acids in water and in aqueous solutions of mono- and disaccharides at 293.15, 303.15, 313.15 and 323.15 K

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Abstract : Apparent molar volumes of malonic and succinic acids have been determined in water and in aqueous solutions of mono- and disaccharides at different temperatures (293.15, 303.15, 313.15 and 323.15 K). The limiting apparent molar volumes (V_{ϕ}^0) and experimental slope (S_{ϕ}) have been obtained in each case. The partial molar volumes (V_2^0) have been used to calculate the partial molar volumes of transfer (ΔV_{ϕ}^0) of malonic and succinic acids from water to aqueous solutions of mono- and disaccharides at different temperatures. The values of limiting apparent molar expansibilities (ϕ_E^0) and that of $(\partial^2 V_{\phi}^0 / \partial T^2)_p$ have been determined from the temperature-dependence of V_{ϕ}^0 . The values of pair (V_{AB}) and triplet (V_{ABB}) coefficients have been determined from ΔV_{ϕ}^0 . It is concluded that both the acids behave as structure makers in water as well as in aqueous solutions of mono- and disaccharides.

Keywords : Apparent molar volumes, malonic and succinic acids, aqueous solutions of mono- and disaccharides.

Introduction

Dash and Mohanty¹ have determined partial molar volumes of homologous dicarboxylic acids in water and in aqueous acetone solutions of varying composition, at different temperatures ranging from 288.15 to 318.15 K. A perusal of the values of partial molar volumes of homologous dicarboxylic acids reported in this study shows that these are not in agreement with the experimental and theoretical values reported in the literature²⁻⁵. Besides, in this study the average value of 11.0 cm³ mol⁻¹ for partial molar volume of -CH₂ group, obtained for homologous dicarboxylic acids in water, is not in agreement with the theoretical value (16.0 cm³ mol⁻¹) obtained by the additivity principle⁶. From the survey of literature, it appears that thermodynamic studies relating to solute-solvent and solute-solute interactions in aqueous solutions of homologous dicarboxylic acids in the presence of mono- and disaccharides are still lacking. Besides, in the back drop of the conflicting results of the above mentioned study of Dash and Mohanty¹, a fresh approach is required as to the value of the partial molar volume of -CH₂ group in respect of two successive mem-

bers of homologous series of dicarboxylic acids. In view of these considerations, thermodynamic studies of solute-solvent and solute-solute interactions in aqueous solutions of malonic and succinic acids in the presence of mono- and disaccharides have been undertaken.

Results and discussion

The apparent molar volumes (V_{ϕ}) of malonic and succinic acids in water and in aqueous solutions of mono- and disaccharides (as solvents) of varying molality (m_s) have been determined, from the density data, as a function of molality (m) of the solutions of the acids at different temperatures using eq. (1),

$$V_{\phi} = \frac{1000 (\rho_0 - \rho)}{m\rho\rho_0} + \frac{M}{\rho} \quad (1)$$

where M is the molecular weight of solute (malonic acid/succinic acid), m is the molality of the solution, ρ and ρ_0 denote the densities of solution and solvent respectively. The representative data are presented in Tables 1 and 2.

The plots of V_{ϕ} versus m are linear (representative Figs. 1 and 2) for both the acids at different tempera-

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Table 1. Densities (ρ) and apparent molar volumes (V_ϕ) of malonic acid as a function of molality (m) in water and in aqueous solutions D(+)-glucose at different temperatures

m (mol kg ⁻¹)	293.15 K		303.15 K		313.15 K		323.15 K	
	10 ⁻³ . ρ (kg m ⁻³)	10 ⁶ . V_ϕ (m ³ mol ⁻¹)	10 ⁻³ . ρ (kg m ⁻³)	10 ⁶ . V_ϕ (m ³ mol ⁻¹)	10 ⁻³ . ρ (kg m ⁻³)	10 ⁶ . V_ϕ (m ³ mol ⁻¹)	10 ⁻³ . ρ (kg m ⁻³)	10 ⁶ . V_ϕ (m ³ mol ⁻¹)
$m_s = 0.0 \text{ mol kg}^{-1}$								
D(+)-Glucose								
0.0000	0.99823	–	0.99568	–	0.99224	–	0.98807	–
0.4117	1.01317	66.82	1.01034	67.69	1.00671	68.42	1.00229	69.33
0.6262	1.02053	67.02	1.01761	67.81	1.01384	68.60	1.00933	69.45
0.8469	1.02784	67.17	1.02473	68.04	1.02082	68.87	1.01637	69.51
1.0742	1.03499	67.42	1.03182	68.21	1.02772	69.11	1.02331	69.65
1.3083	1.04208	67.64	1.03881	68.41	1.03472	69.20	1.03017	69.81
1.5498	1.04904	67.89	1.04579	68.56	1.04148	69.43	1.03702	69.93
1.7986	1.05605	68.04	1.05260	68.78	1.04832	69.55	1.04381	70.06
2.0561	1.06276	68.33	1.05918	69.08	1.05497	69.75	1.05060	70.16
2.3218	1.06953	68.53	1.06580	69.30	1.06143	70.01	1.05721	70.33
$m_s = 0.5307 \text{ mol kg}^{-1}$								
0.0000	1.03223	–	1.02932	–	1.02574	–	1.02136	–
0.3982	1.04621	66.95	1.04297	67.95	1.03905	69.01	1.03438	70.02
0.6057	1.05306	67.17	1.04973	68.06	1.04568	69.06	1.04079	70.17
0.8192	1.05987	67.34	1.05642	68.19	1.05219	69.22	1.04716	70.31
1.0389	1.06666	67.46	1.06302	68.36	1.05867	69.35	1.05346	70.45
1.2652	1.07332	67.64	1.06951	68.56	1.06508	69.49	1.05973	70.57
1.4985	1.07993	67.80	1.07599	68.71	1.07145	69.62	1.06591	70.72
1.7394	1.08635	68.04	1.08232	68.92	1.07776	69.75	1.07206	70.85
1.9878	1.09284	68.19	1.08862	69.09	1.08382	69.99	1.07812	71.01
2.2446	1.09914	68.40	1.09478	69.30	1.08993	70.16	1.08417	71.14
$m_s = 2.5932 \text{ mol kg}^{-1}$								
0.0000	1.13156	–	1.12694	–	1.12254	–	1.11795	–
0.3634	1.14225	68.35	1.13737	69.20	1.13261	70.26	1.12772	71.23
0.5529	1.14753	68.44	1.14245	69.40	1.13760	70.34	1.13253	71.34
0.7481	1.15264	68.68	1.14750	69.54	1.14252	70.45	1.13727	71.47
0.9491	1.15771	68.85	1.15247	69.69	1.14730	70.64	1.14194	71.62
1.1563	1.16267	69.05	1.15721	69.96	1.15214	70.72	1.14655	71.76
1.3700	1.16756	69.24	1.16195	70.15	1.15661	71.02	1.15108	71.91
1.5908	1.17230	69.46	1.16661	70.34	1.16113	71.21	1.15553	72.07
1.6189	1.17694	69.68	1.17118	70.53	1.16558	71.40	1.15986	72.25
2.0550	1.18135	69.96	1.17576	70.68	1.17000	71.56	1.16401	72.48

m_s = Molality of solvent [aqueous solutions of D-(+)-glucose].

tures. Hence, the variation of V_ϕ of malonic and succinic acids with m in water as well as in aqueous solutions of mono- and disaccharides can be represented by the following equation,

$$V_\phi = V_\phi^0 + S_v m \quad (2)$$

where V_ϕ^0 is the limiting apparent molar volume at infinite dilution (which is equal to the partial molar volume of the solute, V_2^0) and S_v is the experimental slope⁷ (some-

Table 2. Densities (ρ) and apparent molar volumes (V_ϕ) of succinic acid as a function of molality (m) in water and in aqueous solutions D(+)-glucose at different temperatures

m (mol kg ⁻¹)	293.15 K		303.15 K		313.15 K		323.15 K	
	10 ⁻³ . ρ (kg m ⁻³)	10 ⁶ . V_ϕ (m ³ mol ⁻¹)	10 ⁻³ . ρ (kg m ⁻³)	10 ⁶ . V_ϕ (m ³ mol ⁻¹)	10 ⁻³ . ρ (kg m ⁻³)	10 ⁶ . V_ϕ (m ³ mol ⁻¹)	10 ⁻³ . ρ (kg m ⁻³)	10 ⁶ . V_ϕ (m ³ mol ⁻¹)
$m_s = 0.0 \text{ mol kg}^{-1}$								
D(+)-Glucose								
0.0000	0.99823	–	0.99568	–	0.99224	–	0.98807	–
0.1010	1.00180	82.50	0.99916	83.63	0.99566	84.53	0.99139	85.89
0.1522	1.00358	82.58	1.00090	83.63	0.99736	84.64	0.99304	85.96
0.2037	1.00535	82.62	1.00262	83.73	0.99905	84.72	0.99469	86.00
0.2557	1.00711	82.71	1.00434	83.82	1.00075	84.72	0.99633	86.07
0.3082	1.00886	82.81	1.00606	83.85	1.00242	84.80	0.99797	86.11
0.3611	1.01060	82.90	1.00777	83.91	1.00410	84.86	0.99961	86.15
0.4145	1.01234	82.96	1.00947	83.98	1.00576	84.94	1.00123	86.22
0.4683	1.01406	83.05	1.01117	84.02	1.00744	84.97	1.00286	86.26
0.5226	1.01581	83.08	1.01286	84.10	1.00911	85.01	1.00446	86.34
$m_s = 0.5307 \text{ mol kg}^{-1}$								
0.0000	1.03223	–	1.02932	–	1.02574	–	1.02136	–
0.0977	1.03552	82.56	1.03250	83.86	1.02884	84.92	1.02435	86.34
0.1471	1.03715	82.63	1.03407	83.98	1.03039	84.92	1.02584	86.36
0.1970	1.03877	82.72	1.03565	84.01	1.03192	84.99	1.02732	86.42
0.2473	1.04038	82.82	1.03722	84.05	1.03345	85.07	1.02881	86.44
0.2980	1.04198	82.91	1.03875	84.20	1.03496	85.17	1.03028	86.49
0.3492	1.04357	83.01	1.04031	84.24	1.03650	85.17	1.03174	86.57
0.4008	1.04516	83.08	1.04186	84.29	1.03798	85.30	1.03320	86.63
0.4529	1.04677	83.11	1.04339	84.37	1.03949	85.34	1.03467	86.66
0.5054	1.04833	83.20	1.04492	84.42	1.04100	85.37	1.03610	86.75
$m_s = 2.5932 \text{ mol kg}^{-1}$								
0.0000	1.13156	–	1.12694	–	1.12254	–	1.11795	–
0.0891	1.13392	83.53	1.12918	84.92	1.12469	86.01	1.11996	87.62
0.1342	1.13508	83.64	1.13029	85.00	1.12575	86.09	1.12096	87.65
0.1798	1.13624	83.70	1.13138	85.09	1.12682	86.10	1.12195	87.71
0.2257	1.13737	83.81	1.13249	85.12	1.12787	86.19	1.12294	87.76
0.2720	1.13852	83.85	1.13357	85.19	1.12890	86.30	1.12391	87.85
0.3187	1.13964	83.96	1.13465	85.26	1.12995	86.32	1.12488	87.90
0.3658	1.14075	84.05	1.13571	85.35	1.13098	86.40	1.12586	87.93
0.4133	1.14185	84.15	1.13676	85.44	1.13202	86.43	1.12683	87.98
0.4613	1.14294	84.24	1.13782	85.49	1.13302	86.52	1.12777	88.05

 m_s = Molality of solvent [aqueous solutions of D(+)-glucose].

times^{8,9} considered to be the volumetric pairwise interaction coefficient). V_ϕ^0 is a measure of solute-solvent interactions¹⁰ while S_v is a measure of solute-solute interactions¹¹. The values V_ϕ^0 and S_v in respect of malonic and succinic acids have been obtained by the least squares

fitting of $V_\phi - m$ data to eq. (2) using a computer. The results with regard to the values of V_ϕ^0 and S_v for malonic and succinic acids are presented in Table 3 along with the standard errors (in the parentheses). The standard deviation (S.D.) of the fit is also mentioned in this Table.

Fig. 1. Plots of apparent molar volume (V_{ϕ}) versus m for malonic acid in water at (○) 293.15; (■) 303.15; (▲) 313.15 and (◆) 323.15 K.

Fig. 2. Plots of apparent molar volume (V_{ϕ}) versus m for malonic acid in aqueous solutions of D(+)-glucose ($m \approx 0.5307$ mol kg^{-1}) at (○) 293.15; (■) 303.15; (▲) 313.15 and (◆) 323.15 K.

From the small values of S.D. it follows that the fit of $V_{\phi} - m$ data to eq. (2) is excellent.

It would not be out of place to mention here the fact that the theoretical values of V_{ϕ}^0 for malonic and succinic acids at 298.15 K obtained from additivity principle¹² are

67.2 $\text{cm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$ (or $67.2 \times 10^{-6} \text{m}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$) and 82.9 $\text{cm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$ (or $82.9 \times 10^{-6} \text{m}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$) respectively which compare fairly well, keeping in view the mode of variation of V_{ϕ}^0 with temperature¹³, with the corresponding experimental values of 67.31 $\text{cm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$ (or $67.31 \times 10^{-6} \text{m}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$) and 83.5 $\text{cm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$ (or $83.5 \times 10^{-6} \text{m}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$) obtained in water at 303.15 K in the present study. It is thus reasonably concluded that the experimental values of V_{ϕ}^0 for malonic and succinic acids at different temperatures (vide Table 3) are compatible with the theoretical values.

From Table 3 it is seen that the values of V_{ϕ}^0 for malonic and succinic acids, in water as well as in aqueous solutions of mono- [D(+)-glucose, D(-)-fructose, L-sorbose] and disaccharides [sucrose and D(+)-maltose (monohydrate)] are largely positive at different temperatures thereby suggesting the presence of strong solute-solvent interactions in these solvent systems. On the other hand, from the values of S_v for both the acids it is found that these are very small in comparison to the values of V_{ϕ}^0 . From this it is inferred that the strength of solute-solute interactions is much smaller as compared to that of solute-solvent interactions.

A close examination of the values of V_{ϕ}^0 in respect of malonic and succinic acids shows that there occurs a difference of 15.91, 16.19, 16.31 and 16.69 $\text{cm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$ at 293.15, 303.15, 313.15 and 323.15 K respectively in purely aqueous solutions. These are in close agreement with the theoretical value of 16.0 $\text{cm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$ for aqueous solutions verified by the experimental data of Sakurai¹⁴.

On comparing the value of V_{ϕ}^0 for malonic and succinic acids in aqueous solutions of mono- and disaccharides (vide Table 4), it is seen that there occurs, on average a difference of about 16.0 $\text{cm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$ ($16 \times 10^{-6} \text{m}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$) at different temperatures and this is equal to the partial molar volume of $-\text{CH}_2$ group [$V_{\phi}^0(\text{CH}_2)$] which is characteristic of two consecutive members of the homologous series of dicarboxylic acids.

On comparing the values of S_v in respect of malonic and succinic acids at different temperatures, both in water as well as in aqueous solutions of mono- and disaccharides, it is found that the values of S_v for malonic acid lie in range 0.3–1.2 while those for succinic acid lie in the range 0.8–1.8. From this it follows that the strength

Table 3. Limiting apparent molar volume (V_{ϕ}^0) and experimental slope (S_{ϕ}) of malonic and succinic acids in water and in aqueous solutions of mono- and disaccharides of varying molality at different temperatures

Molality (m_2) (mol kg ⁻¹) of mono- and disaccharides	$10^6 V_{\phi}^0$ (m ³ mol ⁻¹)			$10^6 S_{\phi}$ (m ³ kg mol ⁻²)			S.D. ^a					
	293.15 K	303.15 K	313.15 K	293.15 K	303.15 K	313.15 K	293.15 K	303.15 K	313.15 K	323.15 K	323.15 K	
Malonic acid												
D(+)-Glucose												
0.0 (water)	66.44 (±0.03)	67.31 (±0.04)	68.15 (±0.07)	69.10 (±0.04)	0.91 (±0.03)	0.84 (±0.04)	0.79 (±0.06)	0.52 (±0.02)	0.0015	0.0011	0.0007	0.0013
0.5307	66.68 (±0.03)	67.61 (±0.03)	68.70 (±0.06)	69.81 (±0.03)	0.77 (±0.03)	0.74 (±0.02)	0.63 (±0.04)	0.59 (±0.02)	0.0008	0.0006	0.0001	0.0015
1.1294	67.21 (±0.03)	68.15 (±0.02)	69.18 (±0.05)	70.34 (±0.02)	0.78 (±0.02)	0.76 (±0.02)	0.64 (±0.03)	0.63 (±0.01)	0.0004	0.0014	0.0012	0.0000
1.8102	67.49 (±0.03)	68.52 (±0.03)	69.48 (±0.06)	70.64 (±0.04)	0.83 (±0.02)	0.67 (±0.02)	0.65 (±0.04)	0.51 (±0.02)	0.0014	0.0002	0.0015	0.0012
2.5932	67.95 (±0.03)	68.89 (±0.040)	69.89 (±0.07)	70.94 (±0.04)	0.96 (±0.03)	0.89 (±0.04)	0.80 (±0.06)	0.72 (±0.03)	0.0009	0.0004	0.0007	0.0013
D(-)-Fructose												
0.5306	66.85 (±0.02)	67.80 (±0.03)	68.75 (±0.02)	69.78 (±0.04)	1.11 (±0.02)	1.01 (±0.03)	0.98 (±0.02)	0.76 (±0.03)	0.0014	0.0008	0.0001	0.0003
1.1298	66.95 (±0.04)	67.87 (±0.03)	68.81 (±0.02)	69.89 (±0.03)	1.14 (±0.04)	1.05 (±0.03)	1.01 (±0.02)	0.84 (±0.03)	0.0017	0.0011	0.0011	0.0010
1.8106	67.05 (±0.02)	67.94 (±0.03)	68.83 (±0.03)	69.86 (±0.04)	1.123 (±0.03)	1.07 (±0.03)	0.99 (±0.03)	0.90 (±0.04)	0.0003	0.0004	0.0002	0.0007
2.5926	67.20 (±0.02)	68.09 (±0.029)	68.95 (±0.02)	69.98 (±0.03)	1.2357 (±0.03)	1.18 (±0.03)	1.02 (±0.02)	0.92 (±0.02)	0.0006	0.0006	0.0012	0.0013
L-Sorbose												
0.5300	66.79 (±0.02)	67.78 (±0.07)	68.75 (±0.06)	69.82 (±0.02)	0.77 (±0.01)	0.71 (±0.05)	0.69 (±0.04)	0.51 (±0.01)	0.0002	0.0013	0.0013	0.0012
1.1272	67.51 (±0.03)	68.48 (±0.03)	69.60 (±0.07)	70.68 (±0.04)	1.03 (±0.03)	1.00 (±0.03)	0.83 (±0.06)	0.63 (±0.02)	0.0013	0.0017	0.0014	0.0015
1.8052	67.66 (±0.05)	68.69 (±0.03)	69.80 (±0.04)	70.95 (±0.04)	1.08 (±0.06)	0.94 (±0.03)	0.81 (±0.03)	0.80 (±0.03)	0.0004	0.0012	0.0014	0.0006
2.5809	68.17 (±0.02)	69.16 (±0.027)	70.17 (±0.03)	71.30 (±0.04)	1.18 (±0.03)	1.05 (±0.03)	0.92 (±0.03)	0.72 (±0.03)	0.0018	0.0007	0.0003	0.0007

Table-3 (contd.)

Sucrose	0.5614	66.76 (±0.02)	67.70 (±0.03)	68.69 (±0.04)	69.76 (±0.05)	1.05 (±0.02)	0.90 (±0.03)	0.80 (±0.04)	0.76 (±0.04)	0.0008	0.0005	0.0002	0.0008
	1.2821	66.81 (±0.04)	67.85 (±0.04)	68.89 (±0.02)	70.09 (±0.03)	1.05 (±0.04)	0.85 (±0.03)	0.83 (±0.02)	0.70 (±0.02)	0.0001	0.0003	0.0010	0.0010
	2.2411	67.06 (±0.03)	67.99 (±0.05)	69.32 (±0.05)	70.60 (±0.04)	1.10 (±0.03)	1.03 (±0.05)	0.92 (±0.05)	0.89 (±0.03)	0.0010	0.0012	0.0013	0.0011
	3.5800	67.74 (±0.03)	68.72 (±0.03)	70.06 (±0.08)	71.05 (±0.07)	1.13 (±0.03)	1.11 (±0.03)	1.02 (±0.09)	0.93 (±0.06)	0.0010	0.0010	0.0012	0.0002
D(+)-Maltose (monohydrate)													
0.1025	66.57 (±0.04)	67.50 (±0.06)	68.38 (±0.07)	69.64 (±0.07)	0.54 (±0.03)	0.50 (±0.04)	0.44 (±0.04)	0.31 (±0.03)	0.0007	0.0002	0.0008	0.0007	0.0007
	66.88 (±0.02)	67.81 (±0.02)	68.84 (±0.02)	69.82 (±0.05)	0.74 (±0.02)	0.65 (±0.02)	0.58 (±0.01)	0.44 (±0.02)	0.0005	0.0001	0.0011	0.0006	0.0006
	68.00 (±0.04)	68.89 (±0.04)	69.76 (±0.05)	70.78 (±0.08)	0.95 (±0.02)	0.80 (±0.02)	0.63 (±0.02)	0.45 (±0.02)	0.0010	0.0004	0.0002	0.0012	0.0012
D(+)-Glucose													
0.0 (water)	82.35 (±0.01)	83.50 (±0.02)	84.46 (±0.02)	85.80 (±0.01)	1.45 (±0.02)	1.15 (±0.02)	1.10 (±0.03)	1.01 (±0.01)	0.0012	0.0007	0.0016	0.0002	0.0002
	82.41 (±0.02)	83.75 (±0.02)	84.77 (±0.02)	86.22 (±0.02)	1.60 (±0.02)	1.13 (±0.03)	1.23 (±0.03)	1.00 (±0.02)	0.0009	0.0013	0.0005	0.0011	0.0011
1.1294	82.61 (±0.01)	83.84 (±0.02)	84.94 (±0.02)	86.41 (±0.03)	1.76 (±0.03)	1.37 (±0.03)	1.32 (±0.03)	1.10 (±0.03)	0.0001	0.0006	0.0007	0.0015	0.0015
	82.87 (±0.01)	84.07 (±0.01)	85.14 (±0.01)	86.66 (±0.02)	1.82 (±0.01)	1.39 (±0.01)	1.36 (±0.02)	1.16 (±0.03)	0.0002	0.0011	0.0009	0.0002	0.0002
2.5932	83.37 (±0.01)	84.79 (±0.01)	85.89 (±0.02)	87.51 (±0.01)	1.87 (±0.02)	1.52 (±0.02)	1.34 (±0.02)	1.16 (±0.02)	0.0005	0.0015	0.0012	0.0001	0.0001
	82.42 (±0.01)	83.63 (±0.02)	84.72 (±0.03)	86.08 (±0.02)	1.57 (±0.02)	1.32 (±0.03)	1.15 (±0.03)	1.12 (±0.02)	0.0005	0.0014	0.0003	0.0012	0.0012
1.1298	82.53 (±0.01)	83.73 (±0.02)	84.85 (±0.02)	86.22 (±0.01)	1.69 (±0.02)	1.46 (±0.02)	1.37 (±0.03)	1.18 (±0.01)	0.0002	0.0002	0.0005	0.0007	0.0007
	82.78 (±0.01)	83.95 (±0.02)	85.07 (±0.01)	86.47 (±0.02)	1.84 (±0.01)	1.48 (±0.02)	1.37 (±0.02)	1.22 (±0.02)	0.0007	0.0015	0.0008	0.0012	0.0012
D(-)-Fructose													
0.5306	82.42 (±0.01)	83.63 (±0.02)	84.72 (±0.03)	86.08 (±0.02)	1.57 (±0.02)	1.32 (±0.03)	1.15 (±0.03)	1.12 (±0.02)	0.0005	0.0014	0.0003	0.0012	0.0012
	82.53 (±0.01)	83.73 (±0.02)	84.85 (±0.02)	86.22 (±0.01)	1.69 (±0.02)	1.46 (±0.02)	1.37 (±0.03)	1.18 (±0.01)	0.0002	0.0002	0.0005	0.0007	0.0007
1.8106	82.78 (±0.01)	83.95 (±0.02)	85.07 (±0.01)	86.47 (±0.02)	1.84 (±0.01)	1.48 (±0.02)	1.37 (±0.02)	1.22 (±0.02)	0.0007	0.0015	0.0008	0.0012	0.0012

Table-3 (contd.)

2.5926	82.86 (±0.01)	84.09 (±0.00)	85.12 (±0.01)	86.51 (±0.01)	1.90 (±0.02)	1.69 (±0.01)	1.59 (±0.02)	1.30 (±0.01)	0.0011	0.0012	0.0005	0.0007
L-Sorbose												
0.5300	82.47 (±0.01)	83.69 (±0.01)	84.73 (±0.01)	86.12 (±0.02)	1.50 (±0.02)	1.27 (±0.02)	1.00 (±0.01)	0.98 (±0.02)	0.0015	0.0002	0.0008	0.0007
1.1272	82.62 (±0.02)	83.79 (±0.01)	84.84 (±0.02)	86.25 (±0.02)	1.71 (±0.03)	1.28 (±0.01)	1.20 (±0.02)	1.07 (±0.02)	0.0018	0.0009	0.0015	0.0015
1.8052	82.77 (±0.01)	83.98 (±0.01)	85.09 (±0.02)	86.48 (±0.02)	1.31 (±0.02)	1.17 (±0.01)	1.07 (±0.02)	0.71 (±0.02)	0.0009	0.0009	0.0015	0.0006
2.5809	83.01 (±0.01)	84.20 (±0.01)	85.26 (±0.01)	86.65 (±0.02)	1.81 (±0.02)	1.71 (±0.01)	1.56 (±0.02)	1.10 (±0.02)	0.0010	0.0007	0.0001	0.0017
Sucrose												
0.5614	82.64 (±0.02)	83.85 (±0.01)	84.87 (±0.02)	86.31 (±0.01)	1.48 (±0.02)	1.47 (±0.02)	0.98 (±0.02)	0.91 (±0.01)	0.0004	0.0011	0.0011	0.0001
1.2821	82.66 (±0.01)	83.88 (±0.02)	85.06 (±0.01)	86.53 (±0.02)	1.59 (±0.02)	1.22 (±0.02)	1.04 (±0.02)	1.03 (±0.02)	0.0007	0.0017	0.0015	0.0001
2.2411	82.72 (±0.01)	84.00 (±0.01)	85.22 (±0.02)	86.64 (±0.02)	1.66 (±0.01)	1.55 (±0.01)	1.49 (±0.02)	1.33 (±0.02)	0.0007	0.0003	0.0000	0.0005
3.5800	82.98 (±0.01)	84.29 (±0.01)	85.57 (±0.01)	87.00 (±0.01)	1.68 (±0.02)	1.60 (±0.02)	1.47 (±0.01)	1.23 (±0.02)	0.0007	0.0017	0.0017	0.0017
D(+)-Maltose (monohydrate)												
0.1025	82.42 (±0.01)	83.58 (±0.01)	84.57 (±0.01)	85.93 (±0.01)	1.36 (±0.02)	1.09 (±0.01)	1.04 (±0.01)	0.82 (±0.01)	0.0014	0.0017	0.0009	0.0007
0.5657	82.73 (±0.01)	83.95 (±0.02)	84.99 (±0.01)	86.44 (±0.02)	1.54 (±0.02)	1.15 (±0.03)	1.11 (±0.02)	1.10 (±0.02)	0.0003	0.0010	0.0016	0.0006
1.3020	83.85 (±0.01)	85.03 (±0.01)	86.04 (±0.02)	87.44 (±0.02)	1.78 (±0.02)	1.55 (±0.01)	1.33 (±0.02)	1.28 (±0.02)	0.0002	0.0001	0.0013	0.0004

Standard errors are given in parentheses.

^aStandard deviation of the fit of eq. (2), $V_{\phi} = V_{\phi}^0 + S_{\phi}m$.

Table 4. Partial molar volume of CH_2 -group, $V_\phi^0(\text{CH}_2)$, of two successive members of dicarboxylic series (malonic acid and succinic acid) in water and in aqueous solutions of mono- [D(+)-glucose, D(-)-fructose and L-sorbose] and disaccharides [sucrose and D(+)-maltose (monohydrate)] at different temperatures

	293.15 K	303.15 K	313.15 K	323.15 K
D(+)-Glucose				
0.0 (water)	15.91	16.19	16.31	16.69
0.5307	15.74	16.14	16.07	16.41
1.1294	15.40	15.68	15.76	16.07
1.8102	15.39	15.55	15.66	16.02
2.5932	15.42	15.90	16.00	16.57
D(-)-Fructose				
0.5306	15.58	15.84	15.97	16.29
1.1298	15.58	15.85	16.04	16.33
1.8106	15.73	16.01	16.24	16.61
2.5926	15.66	16.00	16.17	16.53
L-Sorbose				
0.5300	15.68	15.91	15.98	16.30
1.1272	15.11	15.31	15.24	15.57
1.8052	15.11	15.29	15.29	15.53
2.5809	14.84	15.04	15.09	15.34
Sucrose				
0.5614	15.87	16.14	16.18	16.55
1.2821	15.85	16.03	16.17	16.44
2.2411	15.66	16.01	15.90	16.05
3.5800	15.24	15.57	15.50	15.94
D(+)-Maltose (monohydrate)				
0.1025	15.85	16.08	16.19	16.29
0.5657	15.85	16.14	16.15	16.62
1.3020	15.85	16.14	16.28	16.66

of solute-solute interactions gets increased with the introduction of CH_2 group in the higher homologue (i.e. succinic acid).

Partial molar volumes of transfer, ΔV_ϕ^0 , of malonic and succinic acids from water to aqueous solutions of mono- and disaccharides (as solvents) have been obtained from the following relation,

$$\Delta V_\phi^0 = [V_\phi^0(\text{in aq. solutions of D(+)-glucose/D(-)-fructose/L-sorbose/sucrose/D(+)-maltose (monohydrate)} - V_\phi^0(\text{in water})] \quad (3)$$

It is seen that the values of V_ϕ^0 are positive for both the acids and increase with increasing concentration (m_s) of the cosolute [D(+)-glucose/D(-)-fructose/L-sorbose/sucrose/D(+)-maltose (monohydrate)]. In other words,

there occurs an increase in the volume in going from water to aqueous solutions of D(+)-glucose/D(-)-fructose/L-sorbose/sucrose/D(+)-maltose (monohydrate). The increasing positive values of ΔV_ϕ^0 suggest that in the systems involving malonic acid/succinic acid-water-cosolute (monosaccharides/disaccharides), the ion-hydrophilic and hydrophilic-hydrophilic group interactions are predominant over hydrophilic-hydrophobic group interactions⁶. It is seen that the values of ΔV_ϕ^0 for succinic acid are smaller than those of malonic acid. This observation is in agreement with that reported in the literature^{15,16} wherein the volume of transfer of a homologue, in going from water to non-electrolyte solution becomes lower for its higher homologue. From the fact that ΔV_ϕ^0 increases with the increasing concentration of cosolute (monosaccharides/disaccharides), it may be inferred that in these systems the increased concentration of the mono- and disaccharides leads to the greater ion-hydrophilic and hydrophilic-hydrophilic interactions which are not compensated by hydrophilic-hydrophobic interactions; and this accounts for the predominance of the former over the latter.

The transfer volumes (ΔV_ϕ^0) of malonic and succinic acids can also be expressed by the McMillan-Mayer theory¹⁷ of solutions. Kozak *et al.*¹⁸ have proposed a formalism based on the McMillan-Mayer theory which permits the formal separation of the effects due to interactions between pairs of solute molecules and those due to interactions between three or more solute molecules. This approach has further been discussed by Friedmann and Krishnan¹⁹ and Franks *et al.*²⁰ in order to include the solute-cosolute interactions in the solvation spheres. According to this treatment, a thermodynamic transfer function at infinite dilution, ΔV_ϕ^0 can be expressed as

$$\Delta V_\phi^0 = 2V_{AB} m_s + 3V_{ABB} m_s^2 + \quad (4)$$

where A stands for malonic or succinic acid, B stands for D(+)-glucose/D(-)-fructose/L-sorbose/sucrose/D(+)-maltose (monohydrate) and m_s is the molality of cosolute [D(+)-glucose/D(-)-fructose/L-sorbose/sucrose/D(+)-maltose (monohydrate)], V_{AB} and V_{ABB} are the pair and triplet intermolecular interaction coefficients. The ΔV_ϕ^0 data have been fitted in the above equation to obtain V_{AB} and V_{ABB} , interaction coefficients for malonic and succinic acids which are given in Table 5.

Table 5. Values of pair (V_{AB}) and triplet (V_{ABB}) interaction coefficients for malonic and succinic acids in aqueous solutions of mono- [D(+)-glucose, D(-)-fructose and L-sorbose] and disaccharides [sucrose and D(+)-maltose (monohydrate)] at different temperatures

Temp. (K)	$10^6 \cdot V_{AB}$ ($m^3 \text{ mol}^{-2} \text{ kg}$)		$10^6 \cdot V_{ABB}$ ($m^3 \text{ mol}^{-3} \text{ kg}^2$)	
	Malonic acid	Succinic acid	Malonic acid	Succinic acid
		D(+)-Glucose		
293.15	0.3089	0.0348	-0.0048	0.0414
303.15	0.3897	0.0764	-0.0212	0.0421
313.15	0.5237	0.1441	-0.0499	0.0312
323.15	0.6751	0.2114	-0.0843	0.0269
		D(-)-Fructose		
293.15	0.3020	0.0915	-0.0419	0.0028
303.15	0.3499	0.1179	-0.0536	-0.0004
313.15	0.4965	0.2401	-0.0719	-0.0288
323.15	0.4210	0.2621	-0.0881	-0.0318
		L-Sorbose		
293.15	0.4530	0.1052	-0.0318	0.0057
303.15	0.5474	0.1407	-0.0500	-0.0014
313.15	0.7210	0.2137	-0.0865	-0.0152
323.15	0.8145	0.2600	-0.1018	-0.0252
		Sucrose		
293.15	0.1270	0.1348	0.0092	-0.0096
303.15	0.1871	0.1740	0.0006	-0.0126
313.15	0.3144	0.3325	-0.0097	-0.0332
323.15	0.4708	0.3245	-0.0375	-0.0305
		D(+)-Maltose (monohydrate)		
293.15	0.261	0.1640	0.172	0.2099
303.15	0.375	0.2659	0.119	0.1653
313.15	0.646	0.3724	-0.015	0.1207
323.15	0.801	0.5249	-0.085	0.0543

A perusal of Table 5 shows that the values of V_{AB} for malonic acid in the presence of mono- and disaccharides are positive whereas the values of V_{ABB} are all negative in the presence of D(+)-glucose, D(-)-fructose and L-sorbose. However, in the presence of sucrose and D(+)-maltose (monohydrate) the values of V_{ABB} are positive at 293.15 K and 303.15 K but are negative at 313.15 K and 323.15 K. Further it is also observed that the values of V_{AB} are larger as compared to those of V_{ABB} . Large positive values of V_{AB} indicate an increase in the volume due to hydrogen bonding resulting from the ion-hydrophilic interactions taking place between malonic acid and

cosolute (mono- and disaccharides) molecules.

It is found that the values of V_{AB} for succinic acid (vide Table 5) are positive in the presence of mono- and disaccharides at different temperatures. On the other hand, the values of V_{ABB} are positive in the presence of D(+)-glucose and D(+)-maltose (monohydrate) but are negative in the presence of sucrose. However, in the presence of D(-)-fructose and L-sorbose the values of V_{ABB} are positive at lower temperature (293.15 K) but are rendered negative at higher temperatures. The positive values of V_{AB} for succinic acid indicate an increase in the volume due to hydrogen bonding resulting from ion-hydrophilic interactions taking place between succinic acid and cosolute molecules. The temperature dependence of V_{ϕ}^0 is given by following equation^{21,22},

$$V_{\phi}^0 = a_0 + a_1T + a_2T^2 \quad (5)$$

The values of coefficients a_0 , a_1 and a_2 have been calculated by the least squares fitting of the V_{ϕ}^0 -temperature (T) data into eq. (5) and are listed in Table 6.

The limiting apparent molar expansibilities, ϕ_E^0 of malonic and succinic acids have been calculated²¹ from the following equation,

$$\phi_E^0 = (\partial V_{\phi}^0 / \partial T)_P = a_1 + 2a_2T \quad (6)$$

It is seen that the values of ϕ_E^0 for both the acids are positive in water as well as in aqueous solutions of mono- and disaccharides and the values of ϕ_E^0 for both the acids increase with the rise in temperature thereby showing²³ that malonic and succinic acids behave as structure makers in water as well as in aqueous solutions of mono- and disaccharides.

The values of the derivative, $(\partial^2 V_{\phi}^0 / \partial T^2)_P$ for malonic and succinic acids have been obtained from eq. (5) and are listed in Table 7. These are positive in water and also in aqueous solutions of mono- and disaccharides.

Hepler²⁴ has proposed a method, by which qualitative information on hydration of solutes can be obtained from thermal expansion of aqueous solution by the following relation,

$$(\partial C_P^0 / \partial P)_T = -T(\partial^2 V_{\phi}^0 / \partial T^2)_P \quad (7)$$

According to this, the left hand side of the above equation should be positive for all structure breaking solutes

Table 6. Values of coefficients a_0 , a_1 and a_2 for aqueous solutions of malonic and succinic acids in water and in mono- and disaccharides (as solvents) of varying molality (m_s)

(m_s) (mol kg ⁻¹)	$10^6 \cdot a_0$ (m ³ mol ⁻¹)		$10^6 \cdot a_1$ (m ³ mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹)		$10^6 \cdot a_2$ (m ³ mol ⁻¹ K ⁻²)	
	Malonic acid	Succinic acid	Malonic acid	Succinic acid	Malonic acid	Succinic acid
D(-)-Glucose						
0.0 (water)	62.4	95.2	-0.053	-0.186	0.00025	0.0005
0.5307	76.9	71.8	-0.162	-0.044	0.00045	0.0003
1.1294	85.7	102.3	-0.215	-0.242	0.0005	0.0006
1.8102	66.6	121.8	-0.088	-0.366	0.0003	0.0008
2.5932	64.8	90.0	-0.070	-0.165	0.0003	0.0005
D(-)-Fructose						
0.5306	59.1	82.4	-0.038	-0.109	0.0002	0.0004
1.1298	74.4	86.6	-0.137	-0.137	0.0004	0.0004
1.8106	75.7	102.0	-0.141	-0.236	0.0004	0.0006
2.5926	73.2	85.0	-0.122	-0.122	0.0003	0.0004
L(-)-Sorbitose						
0.5300	56.3	89.3	-0.023	-0.153	0.0002	0.00045
1.1272	61.2	105.7	-0.055	-0.258	0.0003	0.0006
1.8052	64.6	89.6	-0.080	-0.155	0.0003	0.00045
2.5809	71.3	94.7	-0.115	-0.184	0.0004	0.0005
Sucrose						
0.5614	68.1	101.2	-0.099	-0.229	0.0003	0.0006
1.2821	72.9	104.4	-0.138	-0.257	0.0004	0.0006
2.2411	113.7	78.2	-0.412	-0.089	0.0009	0.0004
3.5800	36.5	72.1	0.101	-0.050	0.00002	0.0003
D(+)-Maltose (monohydrate)						
0.1025	115.9	97.3	-0.412	-0.201	0.00085	0.0005
0.5657	50.6	101.6	0.017	-0.233	0.00015	0.0006
1.3020	70.4	100.2	-0.099	-0.213	0.0003	0.0005

and therefore, structure breaking solutes possess negative value of $(\partial^2 V_\phi^0 / \partial T^2)_P$. On the other hand, positive value of $(\partial^2 V_\phi^0 / \partial T^2)_P$ should be associated with structure making solutes. In the present study the positive values of $(\partial^2 V_\phi^0 / \partial T^2)_P$ support the structure making tendency of malonic and succinic acids in purely aqueous solutions as well as in aqueous solutions of mono- and disaccharides. Thus, the positive values of ϕ_E^0 and $(\partial^2 V_\phi^0 / \partial T^2)_P$ lead to the identical conclusion in regard to the structure making tendency of malonic and succinic acids in water as well as in aqueous solutions of mono- and disaccharides.

Experimental

(99.9%) were B.D.H. products of analytical reagent grade and were used as such. The monosaccharides used in this study included D(+)-glucose (Mol. wt. 180), D(-)-fructose (Mol. wt. 180) and L-sorbitose (Mol. wt. 180). These were Merck products of analytical reagent grade of 99.9% purity. The disaccharides, sucrose (Mol. wt. 342) and D(+)-maltose (monohydrate) (Mol. wt. 360) were also Merck products of 99.9% purity.

Solutions of malonic and succinic acids were prepared on molality (m) concentration scale using an electronic balance (Mettler) having an accuracy of $\pm 1 \times 10^{-4}$ g. Double distilled water (specific conductivity $\sim 10^{-6} \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$) was used in the preparation of solutions of the solutes.

Table 7. Values of $(\partial^2 V_\phi^0 / \partial T^2)_P$ for malonic and succinic acids in water and in presence of aqueous solutions of mono- and disaccharides of varying molality (m_s)

m_s (mol kg ⁻¹)	$10^{12} \cdot (\partial^2 V_\phi^0 / \partial T^2)_P$ (m ⁶ mol ⁻² K ⁻²)	
	Malonic acid	Succinic acid
D(+)-Glucose		
0.0 (water)	0.0005	0.0010
0.5307	0.0009	0.0006
1.1294	0.0010	0.0012
1.8102	0.0006	0.0016
2.5932	0.0006	0.0010
D(-)-Fructose		
0.5306	0.0004	0.0008
1.1298	0.0008	0.0008
1.8106	0.0008	0.0012
2.5926	0.0006	0.0008
L-Sorbose		
0.5300	0.0004	0.0009
1.1272	0.0006	0.0012
1.8052	0.0006	0.0009
2.5809	0.0008	0.0010
Sucrose		
0.5614	0.0006	0.0012
1.2821	0.0008	0.0012
2.2411	0.0018	0.0008
3.5800	0.00004	0.0006
D(+)-Maltose (monohydrate)		
0.1025	0.0017	0.0010
0.5657	0.0003	0.0012
1.3020	0.0006	0.0010

The densities of solutions were measured by using digital vibrating tube densimeter (model 60/602 Anton Parr, Austria). The measured densities were accurate to (± 0.003 kg m⁻³) and the precision of measurement was (± 0.001 kg m⁻³). The temperature of the water flowing around the densimeter cell was controlled within ± 0.01 K using an efficient temperature bath.

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